

**PERIMENOPAUSAL SYMPTOMS AND ITS MANAGEMENT BY
AYURVEDA MODALITY – A CASE STUDY**

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ABSTRACT

Pre-menopause refers to the years of menopausal transition during which a woman passes from the reproductive to non-reproductive phase of life, characterized by physical, psychological and emotional changes. Many women in this phase have anovulatory cycles and hyperestrogenism which may lead to several pathological conditions like cervical and endometrial hyperplasia presenting with abnormal uterine bleeding, vaginal discharge, etc. and breast pain due to underlying fibrocystic changes, again due to hormonal fluctuations. In *Ayurvedic* classics *Artava Nivritti* is considered as a normal physiology of *Jaravastha* and hence its effects on body are not explained directly. The treatment available in the contemporary science has a good number of side effects and that in *Ayurveda* are expensive. Further this period belongs to *Parihani Kala* leading to *Vridhnavastha*, therefore *Rasayana*

can be considered. *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* was selected to evaluate its effect in the management of perimenopausal syndrome.

KEYWORDS: Perimenopausal syndrome, *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita*, *Ayurveda*.

INTRODUCTION

Ayurveda conjugation of two Sanskrit words *Ayu* (life) and *Veda* (related to knowledge), literary means the ‘science of life’. It tries to maintain or re-establish harmony between the

mind, body, and forces of nature. This balancing is used for both prevention and treatment of illness.^[1]

A woman sees many phases in her lifetime, right from menarche to pregnancy to puerperium to pre-menopause & finally to menopause. This process involves a wide spectrum of changes in all the aspects of a woman – her body, her mind, her social behaviour. Each woman is unique & each woman's response to the process of menopause may be different & hence this issue needs to be handled with utmost care.

The process of menopause takes a long course & involves many factors & stages. Pre-menopause is one such phase preceding the actual menopause, where immense fluctuations occur in a woman.^[2] Menopause literally means the "end of monthly cycles" from the Greek word *pausis* (cessation) and the root *men-* (month). Menopause is an event that typically (but not always) occurs in women in midlife, during their late 40s or early 50s, and it signals the end of the fertile phase of a woman's life. Peri-menopause is menopause transitional period around menopause (40 – 55years) presenting with psychological and somatic symptoms.^[3]

Prevalence of psychological and somatic symptoms is seen in 80% of women at perimenopausal period.^[3] Some of the women may be asymptomatic or some may have very minimum symptoms which go unnoticed; many may have symptomatic condition which alarms her and her family. In the modern science HRT being the choice of treatment but its effect is limited to physical symptoms only and not to psychological symptoms. 1/3rd of life span women suffers from psychological symptoms like mood disturbance, insomnia, cognitive difficulty, anxiety, depression, memory loss, irritability and somatic symptoms like hot flushes, sexual disturbance etc.

Ayurveda being the science of life has more holistic approach towards tackling issues related to health, life & aging. *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* was one of the important drug formulation explained by *Acharya Charaka*.^[4] It contains *Shatavari*, *Mrudvika*, *Jeevaniya Gana Dravyas*^[5] etc which provides *Bala*, improve immunity, and reduces *Dhatu Kshaya*. Hence, this *Ghrita* was selected for the management of Peri-menopausal syndrome.

OBJECTIVES

To study the effect of *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* in the management of Peri-menopausal syndrome.

METHODOLOGY**CASE STUDY**

Name – XYZ

Age – 43 years old, Female

Occupation – Housewife

Chief complaints of patients

Patient having presenting complaints of Hot flushes, Backache, Excessive sweating, Dryness in vagina and Sleep disturbance since from 2 months. Therefore, for treatment purpose patient came to *Ayurveda* Hospital.

Past History

No any H/O any major illness.

No any Family history, drug or surgical history.

Personal history

- Intake of Non veg – once or twice a week.
- *Diwaswapa, Ratri Jagarana*

General examination of patient

BP = 130/70 mm of Hg

PR = 80 / min

SPO₂ = 99%

Systemic examination

RS = AE=BE, Clear

CVS = S₁S₂ N

CNS = Conscious & well oriented

Management

Management was done with the help of *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* orally 20 ml dose for about 90 days.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESULTS

Observations were noted in this case report as before treatment and after treatment.

Symptoms	0 th day	7 th day	15 th days
Hot flushes	4	1	0
Backache	3	1	1
Excessive sweating	3	1	0
Dryness in vagina	3	1	0
Sleep disturbance	3	1	0

Investigations

Investigations were done with CBC, Serum Calcium, FSH, LH, TSH, Serum estrogen, and Hormonal tests which is done before treatment and after treatment.

Management

Management of Peri-menopausal syndrome were done with *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* which is given for about 90 days of duration before food in morning.

Drug	Matra	Sevana Kala	Anupana
<i>Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita</i>	20 ml	Morning	Koshna Jala

Patients follow up were taken each month up to 90 days. *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* were given along with proper dietary modification, some restrictions, etc.

DISCUSSION

According to *Charaka*, the use of *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* is recommended for the treatment of *Hridroga* (heart diseases), *Unmada* (psychiatric disorders), etc. This *Ghrita* is prepared by combining *Bruhata Shatavari* (*Asparagus racemosus*) with *Ghrita* (ghee) in a specific ratio. It is believed to have rejuvenating properties and can help in the management of various Gynaecological disorders, including *Yoniroga* (genital diseases), *Artava* (menstrual disorders), and *Shukra Dosha* (reproductive disorders). It is advised to consume this *Ghrita* in a prescribed dosage for its therapeutic benefits.

By consuming this *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita*, it can help in the treatment of various conditions such as *Urahkshta*, *Rakatpitta*, acts as *Rasayana* etc. All drugs possess *Balya* properties, which provides strength, improves immune power in the person. Also helps to fulfil *Dhatukshaya*.

CONCLUSION

Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita having properties of *Shoolahara*, *Doshashamaka*, *Balya*, *Rasyana* properties which helps to relieve signs and symptoms in Peri-menopausal symptoms. Also, *Ghrita* has *Santarpana*, *Balya*, *Vrushya* properties. This all ingredients helps to reduces the *Dosha Dushti* along and reduces the hormonal disturbances. In conclusion, *Bruhata Shatavari Ghrita* shows significant results in 90 days of management of Peri-menopausal symptoms along with follow up of proper *Pathya-Apathya*.

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